

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF EMULSIFICATION TEMPERATURE ON CONDUCTANCE OF OIL/OIL EMULSIONS

Oil/oil ratio = 1 : 8, Cetyl alcohol/Acifix = 0.5%

Emulsi- fication temp. °C	Conductance $\times 10^3 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$			
	Kerosene oil/ Ethylene glycol		Turpentine oil/ Ethylene glycol	
	Cetyl alcohol	Acifix	Cetyl alcohol	Acifix
20	5.05	7.10	10.20	12.21
30	5.55	7.65	10.80	12.81
40	5.90	7.95	11.10	13.12
50	6.21	8.27	11.70	13.73
60	6.85	8.90	12.30	14.73

Results and Discussion

The emulsions kerosene oil/ethylene glycol and turpentine oil/ethylene glycol stabilised by cetyl alcohol and Acifix start demulsification as the temperature is increased resulting in continuous increase in conductivity value (Table 1). The effects of demulsification and conductance increase with the rise of temperature are also due to the decrease in the aggregation of particles⁵. Thus it is concluded that as the temperature is increased the demulsification starts and the emulsions become dilute and less stable.

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Synthesis of 2-Arylindoles via Aza-ring Closure of Sulphonium Salts

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MANY routes have been devised to synthesise 2-arylindoles, but the methods are not versatile because the reactions involve drastic reaction conditions. Hirroze *et al.*¹ reported the reaction of *N*-phenacylpyridinium bromide with anilines to furnish 2-phenylindoles. Junjappa² extended this reaction using phenacyldimethylsulphonium bromide. Bansal *et al.*^{3,4} reported the synthesis of indole derivatives by the interaction of phenacylpyridinium and arsonium bromides. These workers

suggested that the reaction occurred by the nucleophilic attack of amino group of aniline on the carbonyl group of pyridinium and arsonium salt to form an intermediate which underwent ylide formation; the latter subsequently cyclised to indole. These observations were in contrast to the suggestion of Junjappa² who reported the course of reaction via an initial ylide intermediate. These contradictory observations led us to reinvestigate the course of reaction of sulphonium ylides and their salts with substituted anilines.

Experimental

The substituted-phenacyl bromides were prepared⁵ by reacting substituted-acetophenones with Br₂ in ether-dioxan solution. All the sulphonium salts (1a-c) were prepared according to the reported procedure⁶⁻⁸.

Reaction of sulphonium salts (1a-c) with aromatic amines:

2-Arylindoles (3a-1): A mixture of sulphonium salt (1a-c) (10 mmol) and aromatic amine (2; 30 mmol) was refluxed in *N,N*-dimethylaniline (50 ml) for 4–8 h. The mixture was then cooled, neutralised with 20% HCl and extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with water, dried (anhydrous Na₂SO₄) and the solvent evaporated to give a solid which was recrystallised from appropriate solvents or solvent mixtures shown in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The method consists of the reaction of *p*-substituted-phenacyldimethylsulphonium bromides (1a-c) with substituted-anilines (2a-1) in dimethylaniline at reflux temperature to give 2-substituted-phenylindoles (3a-1) in 40–70% yields. The reaction can also be carried out using triethylamine, but with lower yield.

A plausible mechanism of the reaction of sulphonium salts (1a-c) with various anilines (2a-1) is similar to that of analogous pyridinium⁹ and arsonium⁴ salts. Another possible route for the formation of indole derivatives (4a-1) could be via initial conversion of the sulphonium bromide (1a-c) to the corresponding ylide. This ylide further reacts with anilines to yield indole derivatives as reported by Junjappa². This possibility was however discarded in view of the fact that the enhanced stability of ylides resulting from delocalisation of negative charge on to carbonyl oxygen was expected to diminish its reactivity towards aniline. This was supported by the observations that the indole derivatives (3a-1) could be obtained by the ylides only when aniline hydrobromide was used. The ylide being a stronger base than aniline, would also react with anilinium bromide to form aniline and the corresponding sulphonium salt (1a-c), the latter was subsequently attacked on

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF 2-ARYLINDOLES (3a-1)

Compd. no.	X	R ¹	R ²	Yield %	M.p.* (Lit)**	$\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) cm ⁻¹	δ (CDCl ₃)
3a	H	H	H	50	184-85 ^a (186-88) ^d	3 402	8.35(1H, b, NH), 6.95(1H, d, C ₆ -H), 7.25-8.10(9H, m, ArH)
3b	H	CH ₃	H	55	116-18 ^b (118-19) ^e	3 445	8.25(1H, b, NH), 6.90(1H, d, C ₆ -H), 2.55(3H, s, CH ₃), 7.20-8.15(8H, m, ArH)
3c	H	H	CH ₃	45	128-30 ^a (134) ^f	3 455	8.20(1H, b, NH), 6.85(1H, d, C ₆ -H), 2.45(3H, s, CH ₃), 7.15-8.18(8H, m, ArH)
3d	H	H	Cl	60	195-96 ^e (195) ^e	3 415	7.55(1H, b, NH), 6.45(1H, d, C ₆ -H), 6.65-7.45(8H, m, ArH)
3e	H	Cl	H	65	112-14 ^a (112) ^f	3 440	7.50(1H, b, NH), 6.50(1H, d, C ₆ -H), 6.75-7.35(8H, m, ArH)
3f	H	NO ₂	H	40	76-78 ^a (80) ^f	3 395	7.65(1H, b, NH), 6.50(1H, d, C ₆ -H), 6.70-7.55(8H, m, ArH)
3g	H	H	NO ₂	45	196-98 ^b (201) ^g	3 398	7.50(1H, b, NH), 6.45(1H, d, C ₆ -H), 6.65-7.40(8H, m, ArH)
3h	Cl	H	H	55	200-02 ^c (204) ^h	3 410	7.75(1H, b, NH), 6.65(1H, d, C ₆ -H), 6.80-7.60(8H, m, ArH)
3i	Cl	H	Cl	70	194-96 ^b (192-93) ^g	3 425	7.85(1H, b, NH), 6.60(1H, d, C ₆ -H), 6.85-7.70(7H, m, ArH)
3j	Cl	Cl	H	65	124-26 ^e (126) ^e	3 418	8.00(1H, b, NH), 6.90(1H, d, C ₆ -H), 7.10-7.80(7H, m, ArH)
3k	Br	H	H	58	208-10 ^b (211) ⁱ	3 410	7.90(1H, b, NH), 6.90(1H, d, C ₆ -H), 7.20-7.80(8H, m, ArH)
3l	Br	H	CH ₃ O	45	202-04 ^a (200) ^j	3 398	7.95(2H, b, NH), 6.95(1H, d, C ₆ -H), 3.85(3H, s, OCH ₃), 7.15-7.80(7H, m, ArH)

*Solvent for crystallisation: ^aC₆H₆-CHCl₃, ^bC₆H₆-CH₂COOC₂H₅, ^cCHCl₃-CH₂OH. **Lit: ^dRef. 9, ^eRef. 10, ^fRef. 11, ^gRef. 12, ^hRef. 13, ⁱRef. 14, ^jRef. 15.

carbonyl group by the nucleophilic aniline (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

The course of reaction initially involves a nucleophilic attack of the anilines (2a-1) on the carbonyl group of the salts (1a-c) to form another sulphonium salt (4) which undergoes ylide formation (5a-1) with aniline base. The ylide, thus formed, attacks the free α -position of the anilines (2) to form the indole derivatives (6a-1) with the elimination of Me₂S (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

All the indoles (3a-1) synthesised were characterised on the basis of elemental analysis, ir and nmr spectral data. In ir spectra, a sharp peak was

found at 3 505–3 360 cm^{-1} attributed to $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ stretching vibration. In pmr spectra, either a broad unresolved peak or a pair of doublets was observed at δ 7.4–8.3 which correspond to NH proton. A doublet centred at δ 6.30–7 was assigned to $\text{C}_8\text{-H}$ proton of the indole nucleus. The aromatic protons were observed at δ 7.00–8.40 (Table 1).

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Synthesis of 2-Substituted-thiobenzimidazoles as Possible Bio-active Agents

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ALTHOUGH introduction of an alkyl or aryl thiopharmacophore at 2- and 5-positions of benzimidazole is generally associated with a broad spectrum of anthelmintic activity¹⁻³, this has not been fully explored in the chemotherapy of intestinal nematodes. These observations have led us to synthesise the structurally related 2-substituted thiobenzimidazoles (3).

Condensation of 4-aminoacetanilide with substituted-aldehydes yielded the corresponding Schiff bases which are hydrolysed to form 4-substituted-benzylideneaminoanilines (1). The second intermediate, 2-chloroacetylthiobenzimidazoles (2) were prepared from benzimidazole-2-thiones⁴ which was synthesised by the reaction of carbon disulphide with the *o*-phenylenediamine, the latter on reaction with chloroacetic acid gave the 2-carboxymethylthiobenzimidazoles⁵. It was reacted with thionyl chloride to form 2. Condensation of the intermediates 1 with 2 in presence of triethylamine gave 2-substituted-thiobenzimidazoles (3).

Experimental

Melting points were determined in sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. The structures of all the compounds were firmly established by their ir and pmr (TMS as internal standard) spectra recorded on Perkin-Elmer 157 infracord and Perkin-Elmer R-32 instruments. Purity of all the compounds was checked by tlc on silica gel G plates using iodine vapours or KMnO_4 spray as visualising reagents.

2-[4-(3'-Nitrobenzylidene amino)acetamidobenzene]thiobenzimidazole (3): A mixture of 3'-nitrobenzylideneaminoaniline (2.41 g, 0.01 mol) and 2-chloroacetylthiobenzimidazole (2.26 g, 0.01 mol) and triethylamine (1.01 g, 0.01 mol) in dry dimethyl formamide was refluxed for 8 h. The resulting mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature and then poured on crushed ice. The solid thus separated was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from acetone, (2.35 g, 50%), m.p. 158° (Found: C, 61.0; H, 3.7; N, 16.0. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_5\text{O}_5\text{S}$ requires: C, 61.30; H, 3.9; N, 16.2%; ν_{max} (KBr) 1 320, 1 560 (NO) and 1 685 cm^{-1} (CONH); δ (DMSO- d_6) 4.74 (2H, s, CH), 6.80–7.40 (15H, m, ArH, NH, N-CH).

Similarly, other compounds of the series were prepared and the results are summarised in Table 1.

Biological activity: Most of the compounds were tested for their antihookworm activity against experimental infection of *Nippostrongylus brasiliensis* in rats (Table 2). The compounds were also screened for their cestocidal activity against *Hymenolepis nana* infection in mice using the technique of Steward⁶ with slight modifications. The compounds were given orally a dose of